

The Mantodea of Carl von Linné

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Abstract. Carl Linné (c. 1707-1778) introduced a total of thirteen species names for Mantodea between 1758-1767. The source material that Linné used for his Mantodea descriptions were either part of his private collection or that of Queen Lovisa Ulrika of Sweden. As an exception to this, one species of Mantodea was described from King Adolf Fredrik's personal collection. Linné's monumental influence within the field of taxonomy and the analysis of his surviving collections have been previously addressed at length through the work of Marshall (1983), Wallin (2001), Jarvis (2007), and Fitton & Harman (2007). The present work summarizes the findings of these previous authors and addresses some lingering concerns that have persisted within Mantodean taxonomy.

Jarvis (2007) documented that Linné had accrued specimens within his personal insect collection for almost three decades prior to his publication of the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae* in 1758. The vast majority of these specimens were not collected by Linné himself but were rather provided to him by his former students (known as "apostles") or through his global network of correspondents in foreign lands. Although Linné was at the employ of Uppsala University as a full professor of medicine during this time, he reportedly did not transfer any of his insect specimens to the university collection. Rather, he kept his collection separate within a private stone-walled museum that he built on his Hammarby farm some six miles away from campus. This particular building has been described as being damp, moldy and infested with vermin and other pests. As such, the collection was prone to damage and briefly fell into neglect upon Linné's death in 1778. Jarvis notes that Linné's widow attempted to sell the collection shortly after Linné passed away but was unable to do so. Linné's son, Carl Linnaeus Jr. (c. 1741-1783), then took ownership of the material and moved it to Uppsala, where he reportedly salvaged what he could and discarded the rest. Carl Linnaeus Jr. created labels for the surviving specimens of his father's collection and added fresh material into the collection up until 1783. In 1784, James Edward Smith (c. 1759-1828), a British botanist and founder of the Linnean Society, purchased the collection and moved it to London, where it has remained ever since.

According to the research conducted by Fitton & Harman (2007), James Smith added a great many specimens into the Linnean collection over the course of his stewardship. The exact number of specimens added by Smith is unknown, as the original Linné material and that of Smith are inextricably commingled, but it is estimated that almost two-thirds of the specimens currently housed within the Linnean collection are not of Linné. Fitton & Harman documented some diagnostic clues that have been used in the past to decipher which specimens are originally of Linné— notably the characteristics of the specimen mounting pins and labels— but the entirety of the collection continues to remain integrated due to the inconsistent reliability of these demarcation methods. Further, there is incontrovertible evidence

that the specimen labels, regardless of their author, have been moved an undetermined amount of times from the specimen pin to the drawer lining and back again, leaving open the possibility of mismatched labels and/or loss.

Four of the thirteen Mantodea species names that were introduced by Linné were based upon specimens that he had described from the collection of Queen Lovisa Ulrika of Sweden. Wallin (2001) tells us that Linné was called upon by the Queen to arrange the material within her cabinets on several different occasions. The curatorial procedure employed by Linné for the Queen's collection consisted entirely of organizing the specimens by his newly formulated groupings and nothing more. Linné reportedly never created any labels for these specimens. Wallin further advised that Linné conducted the curation of the Uppsala University insect collection in the same manner, in that he generated no labels for the specimens that he organized. It is strongly suspected by the present author that Linné generated no labels whatsoever— at least not any that have survived in association with Mantodea.

In 1804, The Queen's insect collection was donated to Uppsala University by her grandson, Gustav IV Adolf. Carl Thunberg (c. 1743-1828), an apostle of Linné and professor of medicine at the university, cataloged the donation and furnished each specimen with identification labels for the first time by his own hand. As with Linné's private collection, the determination of the true type specimens within the Museum Lodovisa Ulrika (MLU) has been complicated by the addition of new material by Thunberg and his own labeling of Linné's material. Wallin concludes that Linné did not label any of the specimens currently housed within the Linnaean collection. These labels were instead created by Carl Linnaeus Jr., James Smith or Carl Thunberg. As such, the genuine type status as well as the accuracy of the species determination of these specimens is called into question.

There are several additional points to consider when reviewing Mantodea taxonomy as it relates to Linné:

1) Linné was a prolific author of botany and zoology who was professionally employed as a physician/professor. He was a pioneering taxonomist and the author of over twelve thousand species of plants and animals. There was no governing body of taxonomy in Linné's time and the very concept of naming species was a novel idea. With such an impressively diverse array of expertise and knowledge, Linné was still only one man who lived in 18th century Sweden. He was entirely reliant upon others providing him with specimens and the collection data of these specimens was either sparse to nonexistent and poorly recorded regardless. Because of this, Linné erroneously documented the origin of many species, he cited historical references of unrelated species within his descriptions, and he occasionally named the same specimen more than once— sometimes intentionally so.

2) There are three species that were authored by Linné that have been historically misattributed to Johansson. These are: *carolinus*, *irrorata*, and *unicornis*. As Marshall (1983: 376) argues, Johansson was a student of Linné whose role was to defend a thesis written by his professor to demonstrate his command of Latin. Thus, Linné authored the original descriptions of these three species that first appeared in *Centuria Insectorum Rariorum* and Johansson merely defended the work. Such practices were not isolated to Linné, as Thunberg, Afzelius and Fries also had Latin theses defended by their students but in all cases the species described therein were attributed to them and not their students. Further, the descriptions of these three species within *Centuria Insectorum Rariorum* from 1763 are identical to those of Linné's *Amoenitates Academicæ* Volume 6 from later in that same year in which he included no reference to Johansson. Marshall finally points out that most Scandinavian authorities on Linnaean taxonomy regard Linné as the author of *Centuria Insectorum Rariorum* and, in the name of nomenclatural stability, it would be prudent to practice consistency.

3) Linné did not designate any type specimens among the taxa that he described. For those species that he described from a single specimen, the holotype is fixed by monotypy (ICZN Article 73.1.2). For those

species that were described from a series of specimens, these are automatically designated as syntypes (ICZN Article 73.2).

4) Linné used several Latin terms within his species descriptions that conflict with modern morphological terminology as it pertains to entomology. These terms along with their modern equivalents are:

Pedes 1. Femora = prothoracic coxae

Pedes 1. Tibiae = prothoracic femora

Pedes 1. Palmae or Tarsus = prothoracic tibiae

Pedes 1. Digitus = prothoracic tarsi

Pedes 2. 3. Femora & Tibiae = meso/metathoracic femora & tibiae

Pedes 2. 3. Tarsi = meso/metathoracic tarsi

With these points in mind, let us now turn to the Mantodea names that were introduced by Linné. They are as follows:

-bicornis. *Systema Naturae*, 1758: 426. Linné established the genus *Gryllus* within *Amoenitates Academicæ* Volume 1 in 1749 to incorporate the Orthopteroid insects. This genus was later subdivided into six subgenera, one of which was *Mantis*, which was established in the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae* in 1758. Linné elevated *Mantis* to the rank of genus within the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae* in 1767. He described *Gryllus (Mantis) bicornis* from a specimen that he had analyzed from Queen Ulrika's collection. As we learn from Wallin (2001: 3), Linné had prepared a detailed catalog of this collection prior to 1754 but it was delayed in printing and was not published until 1764. This *Museum Ludovicae Ulricae Reginae* work focused exclusively upon those specimens found within the Queen's collection and the species descriptions therein are far more detailed than the description summaries found within the *Systema Naturae* series. While this manuscript was awaiting publication, Linné moved forward with the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he provided the first published description of *bicornis* within three short lines of text, written in Latin. The holotype is evidently male, as the long-form description from 1764 detailed both the forewings and hindwings of this sexually dimorphic species. Linné republished the original description summary of this species within the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he transferred *bicornis* to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. There is presently no surviving specimen or label of *bicornis* within the MLU or any specimen that could be mistaken as this distinctive species. The holotype has therefore been lost. As there are no records or indications of specimens being traded into or transferred out of Queen Ulrika's cabinets, this specimen is believed to have been destroyed over time due to its fragile morphology that would make it more prone to suffer breakage.

Schizocephala bicornis (Linné, 1758)

Gryllus (Mantis) bicornis Linné, 1758

Mantis bicornis Linné, 1767

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Figure 1: Nontype of *Mantis carolina* ♀ (left) with Smith and Gabriel labels pinned to specimen (right). The Linnean Society of London insect collection: LINN 8869. Permission of the Linnean Society of London.

-*carolinus*. Centuria Insectorum Rariorum, 1763: 13-14. In 1763, Linné described *Gryllus* (*Mantis*) *carolinus* from a specimen that had been sent to him from Garden. Dr. Alexander Garden (c. 1730-1791) was a Scottish physician, botanist and zoologist who resided for many years in Charles Town in the Province of South Carolina (modern day Charleston, South Carolina, USA). Garden was known to have shipped flora and fauna specimens from the British province in North America to Linné in Sweden. The original description of *carolinus* has been historically attributed to Johansson in error. Linné published a description summary of this species in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae* from 1767, wherein he unjustifiably emended *carolinus* to *carolina* and referenced the preceding long-form description that was published in *Amoenitates Academicæ* and not the thesis defended by Johansson. The holotype of *carolina* was evidently female, as the original description detailed the abbreviated wings of this sexually dimorphic species.

The Linnean Society insect collection contains one female specimen of *carolina* (Figure 1). The accompanying label has “carolina ?” inscribed, which indicates that it was created by Smith, as Linné would not have a query about his own holotype. Further, this specimen is in remarkably good condition considering its alleged age and does not exhibit the typical damage as other confirmed types of Linné that survived the harsh conditions of his Hammarby museum. Thus, this specimen seems to have been added to the Linnean collection by Smith during his stewardship, indicating that the holotype was likely destroyed and discarded by Carl Linnaeus Jr. upon him taking ownership of his father’s material prior to Smith purchasing the collection. The white paper strip label with the typewritten “9” was created by Alfred G. Gabriel, who rehoused and curated the Linnean collection of insects in 1929. This notation corresponds to the species number from the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae* that was published in 1767.

Stagmomantis (*Stagmomantis*) *carolina* (Linné, 1763)
Gryllus (*Mantis*) *carolinus* Linné, 1763
Gryllus (*Mantis*) *carolinus* Johansson, 1763 **attributio erroris**
Mantis carolina Linné, 1767

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Figure 2: Syntype of *Mantis gongylodes* (nymph) with Thunberg label attached to drawer (left) and Thunberg label pinned to specimen (right). Additional blue label provided by Uppsala University for cataloging. Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University.

Figure 3: Nontypes of *Mantis gongylodes* ♀. Specimen without label (left) and specimen with Smith and Gabriel labels (right). The Linnean Society of London insect collection: LINN 8862 & LINN 8861. Permission of the Linnean Society of London.

-*gongylodes*. *Systema Naturae*, 1758: 426. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) gongylodes* from two specimens, an adult female and juvenile, that he had analyzed from Queen Ulrika's collection. The detailed long-form description of both of these specimens was provided within *Museum Ludovicae Ulricae Reginae*. Prior to the publication of this work, Linné had published a description summary of *gongylodes* within the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he indicated that a nymph had also been

analyzed. The description of the nymph was expanded for the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae* and this species was transferred to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. The only surviving specimen of *gongylodes* within the MLU is the nymph syntype (Figure 2). The adult female syntype has been lost. As Linné did not create any labels for the specimens of Queen Ulrika’s collection, a new label was created by Thunberg upon the collection being donated to Uppsala University by the Queen’s grandson. There are presently two labels associated with the nymph syntype, both of Thunberg’s hand. The larger of the two reads: “gongylodes larva, Mus. Regin. p. 113. Mus. Gust. Adolphi,” which indicates the page number within *Museum Ludovicae Ulricae Reginae* and the Museum Gustavo-Adolphianum, which is the donation of Gustav IV Adolf of Queen Ulrika’s collection to the university. The smaller label reads: “gongylodes. larva, typus.” and is attached to the specimen pin to presumably prevent potential label mismatching in the future. There are two additional specimens of *gongylodes*, both adult females, that were part of Linné’s private collection. These specimens were very likely collected by Johan König, one of Linné’s apostles who collected for him in south India. One of the specimens bears no label at all. The second specimen has a Smith label that reads “*gongylodes*” and a Gabriel label with the typewritten “4” to reference the species number from the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*.

Gongylus gongylodes (Linné, 1758)
Gryllus (Mantis) gongylodes Linné, 1758
Mantis gongylodes Linné, 1767

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Figure 4: Mislabeled nontype of *Mantis irrorata* ♀ (left) with Linnaeus Jr. and Gabriel labels (right). The Linnean Society of London insect collection: LINN 8868. Permission of the Linnean Society of London.

-irroratus. *Centuria Insectorum Rariorum*, 1763: 14. This species was described by Linné alongside *carolinus* and it too originated from the Province of South Carolina and is also believed to have been procured by Alexander Garden. Due to the extreme variability in pigmentation of this taxon, Linné believed that the two female specimens from the American colony represented distinct species– the brown phase/heavily mottled *carolinus* and the green phase/lightly mottled *irroratus*. Both long-form original descriptions first appeared in *Centuria Insectorum Rariorum* and were reprinted verbatim in *Amoenitates Academicæ* Volume 6 later that same year. As in the case of *carolinus*, the author of *irroratus* has been

historically misattributed to Johansson. Linné published a description summary of this species in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he emended *irroratus* to *irrorata* and transferred this species to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. Linné noted at this time that *irrorata* was similar to *precaria* but differed in having shortened elytra and wings.

The Linnean Society insect collection contains one female specimen of *irrorata* (Figure 4). The accompanying label has “7 precarius” inscribed. As Fitton & Harman (2007: 54) point out, the narrow labels within the Linnaean collection that typically have the trivial name accompanied by a species number that references the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae* were created by either Linné or his son. This is further evidenced by the much different handwriting of these labels in comparison to those made by Smith. In this case, it is evident that Carl Linnaeus Jr. created this particular label and misidentified the *irrorata* specimen as *precarius*. The only known specimen of *precarius* at this time was deposited in Queen Ulrika’s collection and Linné made no literary reference to having this species represented in his own collection. Further, it has yet to be confirmed that Linné ever referenced his own work on his own labels with numbered notations— if he created any labels at all. A more plausible scenario in this case is that the holotype of *irrorata* had fallen victim to the rough conditions of Linné’s private museum, as did the type of *carolina* and many others, and the remains of the specimen were discarded by Carl Linnaeus Jr. upon his moving the collection to Uppsala. Then, as he added fresh material into the collection, Linné’s son misidentified a new *irrorata* specimen as *precarius*, and created a label for it that referenced the species number from his father’s 10th edition of *Systema Naturae*. Irrespective of the origin of this specimen, we know that it is not the holotype of *irrorata* nor is it a representative of *precarius*, as it does not align with either species original description. Regarding the original description of *irrorata*, Linné noted that the elytra are maculated with “rusty points distributed without order, the tips yellowish”. This particular specimen represents a variable color form of *irrorata* that does not have mottled greenish-brown forewings. Regarding *precarius*, Linné described this species as having the lateral margins of the pronotum armed with short spines and the forewings bearing a “large reddish eyespot with yellow pupil in middle of tegmina near costa.” Both of these highly distinctive characters are absent in this specimen.

The Gabriel label with the typewritten “8” corresponds to the species number for *precaria* from the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*. Fitton & Harman (2007: 51) documented that Gabriel curated, cleaned and mended the Linnean specimens as he transferred them from their previous drawers into new glass-lidded boxes in 1929. He did not challenge any of the taxonomic identifications of the specimens so his generation of the typewritten label was merely for cataloging purposes and is not an endorsement of the species determination. It is quite obvious that this particular specimen suffered a breakage of the pronotum away from the main body and is missing the head capsule. Gabriel evidently attempted to repair this specimen and haphazardly glued the headless prozona into the body.

Stagmomantis (Stagmomantis) carolina (Linné, 1763)
= *Gryllus (Mantis) irroratus* Linné, 1763
Gryllus (Mantis) irroratus Johansson, 1763 **attributio erroris**
= *Mantis irrorata* Linné, 1767

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Figure 5: Mislabeled holotype of *Mantis masculus* ♀ with Thunberg label attached to drawer (left), ventral habitus of same specimen (right) and Thunberg label pinned to specimen (bottom). Additional blue label provided by Uppsala University for cataloging. Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University.

-masculus. Museum Ludovicae Ulricae Reginae, 1764: 115. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) masculus* from a female specimen that he had analyzed from Queen Ulrika's collection. Although Linné documented the habitat of this species as "southern Europe," it is clearly of African origin. The collector of this specimen is unknown. As with all of the material that Linné had organized within the Queen's collection, this specimen was without a label when it was donated to Uppsala University in 1804. Thunberg created two labels for this specimen during his curation of the MLU donation. The first label remains affixed to the drawer bottom and reads: "Precaria. β. ?. Mus. Gust. Adolph." The smaller label that remains pinned to the specimen reads only "precarias β". The donation reference from the larger label is clear. What remains more ambiguous is the species determination that was made by Thunberg.

Within the original description of *masculus* from 1764, which matches the "precarias β" specimen quite well, we read that Linné queried whether this species is the conspecific male of *precarius* and is distinguished only by the "spot of the arms". Thunberg apparently followed this suggestion and tentatively diagnosed this specimen as the "beta" form of *precarius*. However, it is evident that this specimen has no relation to *precaria* and is actually the first described specimen of *Polyspilota aeruginosa* (Goeze, 1778), making *Gryllus (Mantis) masculus* the senior synonym of the two names. *Polyspilota aeruginosa* (Goeze, 1778) is a well known name that is associated with a ubiquitous African species, whereas *Gryllus (Mantis) masculus* has not been used as a valid name for 259 years. Further, *aeruginosa* has been used as a presumed valid name in a great many works that have been published over the last few decades alone. Thus, both conditions of the ICBN Article 23.9 reversal of precedence clause are met, rendering the younger but valid name *nomen protectum*.

Linné listed the original description of *masculus* as a reference for *oratoria* within the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*. This later species has no relation to *masculus* and has distinctive hindwing maculation characters in addition to having a much smaller habitus.

Polyspilota aeruginosa (Goeze, 1778) **nomen protectum**
 = *Gryllus (Mantis) masculus* Linné, 1764 **nomen oblitum**

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-ocellatus. Hans Majestatis Adolf Frideriks, 1754: 82. *Gryllus ocellatus* is the earliest known Latin binomial assigned to any species of Mantodea. This name was used by Linné to describe a specimen that he had examined from King Adolf Fredrik's personal collection. King Fredrik (c. 1710-1771) was husband to Queen Lovisa Ulrika of Sweden and he maintained a separate collection from the Queen. Linné arranged both of the monarch's collections at the request of the royal family and composed a detailed catalog for each. The catalog for the Queen's collection, *Museum Ludovicae Ulricae Reginae*, was written first but was delayed in publishing and was not released until 1764. The catalog for the material within the King's collection, *Hans Majestatis Adolf Frideriks*, was published in 1754. Linné referenced the manuscript of the Queen's catalog within this work, as he did in several other subsequent articles, before it was actually published. The published version of the *M.L.U.* includes a detailed description of a female specimen that Linné analyzed from Queen Ulrika's collection that he named *Gryllus (Mantis) precarius*. The description summary of this species is very similar to that of *ocellatus*:

Original description of *ocellatus* from 1754: “*thorace elongato lineari subciliato, elytris flavis: ocello ferrugineo*”

Original description summary of *precarius* from 1764: “*thorace subciliato, elytris flavis ocello ferrugineo*”

Linné cites the description of *Gryllus ocellatus* from *Hans Majestatis Adolf Frideriks* as a reference for *precarius* as well as the earlier description summary of *precarius* from the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae*. Thus, Linné evidently examined two conspecific specimens— one from the King's collection and the other from the Queen's collection, both of them female. He established two different names for these, calling the specimen from the King's collection *ocellatus* and the one from the Queen's collection *precarius*. As the *ocellatus* name was published first, it is the senior synonym. However, this name was overlooked very soon after it was published and *precaria* has been used as a presumed valid name for over 250 years. Thus, both conditions of the ICZN Article 23.9 reversal of precedence clause are met, rendering the younger but valid name *nomen protectum*. The dry material from the King's collection was reportedly transferred to Uppsala University but the holotype of *ocellatus* has not been recovered.

Stagmatoptera precaria (Linné, 1758) **nomen protectum**
Gryllus ocellatus Linné, 1754 **nomen oblitum**

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Figure 6: Holotype of *Mantis oratoria* ♂ (left) with Smith and Gabriel labels (right). The Linnean Society of London insect collection: LINN 8867. Permission of the Linnean Society of London.

-oratorius. *Systema Naturae*, 1758: 426. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) oratorius* from a specimen that he had reportedly received from Brander. Erik Brander was one of Linné's correspondents who provided material for him from Algeria and North Africa. Linné documented that this species originates from Africa, making Algeria the most likely type locality. Linné republished the original description summary of this species in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he emended *oratorius* to *oratoria* and transferred this species to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. Linné also noted at this time that this species occurs in Europe and he cited four additional references within the species treatment. One of the references was his own work from 1764 that pertained to *masculus*, as previously noted. The other three references are from Muffët (1634), Rosel (1749) and Geoffroy (1762), all of which are pre-Linnaean treatments and illustrations of *religiosa*.

The Linnean Society insect collection contains one male specimen of *oratoria* (Figure 6). This specimen is tentatively regarded as the holotype of this species. There is no indication within the original description of *oratoria* as to the sex of the holotype. Linné documented that the forewings were green, which could indicate that the holotype was female, given the opaque nature of female *oratoria* forewings, in which case the male specimen within the Linnean Society collection is not the holotype and was instead provided by Smith. But there is also no explicit notation by Linné in the original description that the forewings were either entirely green or just partially green, nor is there any mention of the wings being abbreviated, as is typical for females. But these conjectures, combined with the relatively good condition of the Linnean Society specimen, continue to cast doubt on its type status. For now, there is not enough firm evidence to deny the specimen's typification so it should remain regarded as the holotype. The accompanying label for this specimen has "oratorius" inscribed and was evidently created by Smith. The Gabriel label with the typewritten "6" corresponds to the species number for *oratoria* from the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*.

Iris oratoria (Linné, 1758)

Gryllus (Mantis) oratorius Linné, 1758

Mantis oratoria Linné, 1767

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Figure 7: Holotype of *Mantis precaria* ♀ with Thunberg label attached to drawer (left), ventral habitus of same specimen (right) and Thunberg label pinned to specimen (bottom). Additional blue label provided by Uppsala University for cataloging. Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University.

-*precarius*. *Systema Naturae*, 1758: 426. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) precarius* from a female specimen that he had analyzed from Queen Ulrika's collection. The collector of this specimen is unknown. As with the other Mantodea that Linné had organized within the Queen's collection, this specimen was without a label when it was donated to Uppsala University in 1804. Thunberg created two labels for this specimen during his curation of the MLU donation. The smaller label that remains pinned to the specimen reads only "precarius, typus". The larger label that remains affixed to the drawer bottom reads: "Precaria. α. Mus. Gust. Adolph." This larger label references Gustav IV Adolf's donation of Queen Ulrika's collection to the university and Thunberg's designation of this specimen as the "alpha" form of *precarius* to distinguish it from *masculus*. Linné republished the description summary of this species in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he emended *precarius* to *precaria* and transferred this species to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. Although the description summary of this species that was provided in the 10th and 12th editions of *Systema Naturae* is somewhat wanting, the long-form description from *Museum Ludovicae Ulricae Reginae* is quite detailed and matches the type specimen that has survived within the MLU quite well.

The treatment of "*Stagmatoptera precaria*" by Rodrigues & Canello (2016: 42-47) does not match the holotype of *precaria* or Linné's original description of this species. However, these authors treated another species within the same publication that they refer to as *supplicaria* Burmeister, 1838 that matches well with Linné's diagnosis for *precaria*. It would thus appear that Rodrigues & Canello have these two species exactly reversed. But as mentioned in their remarks concerning *supplicaria*, this later name was introduced by Burmeister (1838: 542) to re-name "The Devout Mantis" that was illustrated within Stoll's publication from 1787. Stoll's illustration of this distinctive species matches very closely to the holotype of *precaria* and Lichtenstein (1796: 79), Manuel (1797: 628), Latreille (1807: 93) and Houttuyn (1813: 78) all properly referred to this illustration as representing *precaria*. Given that Burmeister established *supplicaria* entirely from Stoll's illustration of *precaria*, these two names are synonyms, with *precaria* being the senior. Therefore, Rodrigues & Canello's treatment of *supplicaria*

actually refers to the genuine *precaria* and the distinct species that they refer to as “*precaria*” requires a different name.

Anderson (2022: 75) thoroughly reviewed the entirety of Stoll’s work and erroneously concluded, based on Rodrigues & Canello’s treatment of “*precaria*,” that Stoll’s “The Red and White-Eyed Mantis” and “The Great Green Mantis” represent a male and female of *precaria* respectively. These two specimens from Stoll are conspecific and are the first known representatives of the distinct species that Rodrigues & Canello refer to as “*precaria*.” “The Red and White-Eyed Mantis” is the male of this species and was described by Stoll in 1787. “The Great Green Mantis” is the conspecific female and was described later by Stoll in 1813. As Anderson detailed, “The Red and White-Eyed Mantis” was assigned its first Latin binomial in 1797 by Manuel (erroneously attributed to Olivier, 1792), who called it *Mantis ocellata*. Whether Manuel was referencing Linné’s *ocellatus* from 1754 or if he just coincidentally assigned the same epithet of Linné to Stoll’s specimen matters not, as this name is preoccupied and cannot be used for this distinct species. The next valid name that was assigned to “The Red and White-Eyed Mantis” is *Mantis obsecraria* Lichtenstein, 1802. With this name being the first available epithet assigned to this species, it should be resurrected as a valid species name for Rodrigues & Canello’s “*precaria*”.

Stagmatoptera precaria (Linné, 1758)

Gryllus (Mantis) precarius Linné, 1758

Mantis precaria Linné, 1767

= *Mantis supplicaria* Burmeister, 1838 **n. syn.**

Stagmatoptera obsecraria (Lichtenstein, 1802) **stat. res.**

Mantis obsecraria Lichtenstein, 1802

= *Mantis ocellata* Manuel, 1797 **n. syn.**

= *Mantis annulata* Houttuyn in Stoll, 1813 **n. syn.**

= *Mantis rogatoria* Houttuyn in Stoll, 1813 **n. syn.**

= *Stagmatoptera precaria* (Linné, 1758) *sensu* Rodrigues & Canello, 2016

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Figure 8: Holotype of *Mantis religiosa* ♂ with Smith and Gabriel labels (left) and nontype of *Mantis religiosa* ♀ without label (right). The Linnean Society of London insect collection: LINN 8863 & LINN 8864. Permission of the Linnean Society of London.

Figure 9: Nontype of *Mantis religiosa* ♀ with Smith label (left) and nontype of *Mantis religiosa* ♀ without label (right). The Linnean Society of London insect collection: LINN 8866 & LINN 8865. Permission of the Linnean Society of London.

-religiosus. *Systema Naturae*, 1758: 426. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) religiosus* from a single male specimen that he had reportedly received from Brander. He documented that this species originated from Africa, making Algeria the most likely type locality, given the known locale of Brander's collecting expedition. Linné republished the original description summary of this species in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he emended *religiosus* to *religiosa* and transferred this species to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. Linné also noted at this time that this species occurs in Austria and he

cited three additional references within the species treatment, which he expanded to include a more detailed description of the forewings and prothoracic legs.

The Linnean Society insect collection contains four specimens of *religiosa*, one male holotype and three nontype females (Figures 8-9). The male holotype matches the original description and demonstrates damage from being stored at Linné's Hammarby museum. The accompanying label for this specimen has "religiosus" inscribed and was evidently created by Smith, who utilized the original spelling of the epithet from the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae*, as he had done with *oratorius*. The Gabriel label with the typewritten "5" corresponds to the species number for *religiosa* from the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*. The three nontype females were added to the Linnaean collection by Smith, given their remarkably better condition. Two of these specimens are devoid of labels. One has a Smith label that reads "Montpellier 1786". As such, these three nontypes were likely provided to Smith by his correspondent, Jacob Anselm Dorthes, who resided in Montpellier, France.

Mantis religiosa (Linné, 1758)

Gryllus (Mantis) religiosus Linné, 1758

Mantis religiosa Linné, 1767

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-*strumarius*. *Systema Naturae*, 1758: 426. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) strumarius* from a specimen that had reportedly originated from "Indiis". He republished the original description of this species in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he emended *strumarius* to *strumaria* and transferred this species to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. The type specimen of *strumaria* has been lost but it is believed to have been a male, given the description of its pronotal shape. The original description reads: "*thorace utrinque membranaceo-dilatato obcordato*," which roughly translates to "thorax membranous-dilated from both sides in obcordate shape". The "obcordato" adjective is a botanical term that refers to the shape of leaves. An obcordate leaf is one that is heart-shaped and attached to the stalk by the pointed end. This descriptor is very important to the species diagnosis, as it positively distinguishes the pronotal shape of *strumaria* and confirms its rightful placement within *Choeradodis* Serville, 1831. Linné cited an illustration of a *Choeradodis* specimen by Rosel (1749) within the original description of *strumaria* and cited an additional illustration by Merian (1705) within the relisting of this species for the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*. The type locality of this species is in error. It most likely originated from Surinam, where it was probably collected by Daniel Rolander, an apostle of Linné who visited the Dutch colony.

Choeradodis strumaria (Linné, 1758)

Gryllus (Mantis) strumarius Linné, 1758

Mantis strumaria Linné, 1767

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Figure 10: Holotype of *Mantis tricolor* ♀ with Thunberg label attached to drawer (left) and Thunberg label pinned to specimen (right). Additional blue label provided by Uppsala University for cataloging. Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University.

-tricolor. *Systema Naturae*, 1758: 426. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) tricolor* from an adult female that he had analyzed from Queen Ulrika's collection. The detailed long-form description of this specimen was provided within the *Museum Ludovicae Ulricae Reginae* work that was not published until 1764. Prior to this printing, Linné had published a description summary of *tricolor* within the 10th edition of *Systema Naturae*. The description summary was republished for the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae* when this species was transferred to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. The holotype remains within the MLU (Figure 10). As Linné did not create any labels for the specimens of Queen Ulrika's collection, a new label was created by Thunberg upon the collection being donated to Uppsala University by the Queen's grandson. There are presently two labels associated with the holotype, both of Thunberg's hand. The larger of the two reads: "tricolor. Mus. Gust. Adolph," which refers to the donation of Gustav IV Adolf of Queen Ulrika's collection to the university. The smaller label reads: "3-color, typus." and is attached to the specimen pin. Linné erroneously documented that this African species originated from "Indiis". The collector is unknown.

Harpagomantis tricolor (Linné, 1758)
Gryllus (Mantis) tricolor Linné, 1758
Mantis tricolor Linné, 1767

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Figure 11: Nontypes of *Empusa pennata* ♂. Male specimen with Smith label (left) and female specimen without label (right). The Linnean Society of London insect collection: LINN 8870 & LINN 8871. Permission of the Linnean Society of London.

-unicornis. Centuria Insectorum Rariorum, 1763: 13. Linné described *Gryllus (Mantis) unicornis* from a male specimen that had reportedly originated from China. Although Pehr Osbeck (c. 1723-1805) was an apostle of Linné who collected fauna and flora specimens for him from China, it is unlikely that Osbeck was the collector of this particular specimen. The extent of Osbeck's expedition was confined to the southeastern coastal province of Guangdong (and Java), where *Empusa* Illiger, 1798 does not occur. Thus, the collector of this specimen is unknown. As in the case of *carolinus* and *irroratus*, the author of this species has been historically misattributed to Johansson. Linné published only the description summary of this species in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae*, wherein he transferred this species to the newly upgraded genus *Mantis* and introduced the objective synonym *pectinicornis* for *unicornis*.

The male holotype of *unicornis* has been lost. However, the Linnean Society insect collection has one male, one female, and two nymphs of a conspecific series of *Empusa pennata* (Thunberg, 1815) from southern France that are databased under "*Gryllus unicornis*". Only one of these specimens, the male, contains a label. This label was authored by Smith and reads "Montpellr. Dorthes.", which is a collection location/collector reference to Smith's correspondent, Jacob Dorthes of Montpellier, France. There is no species determination label associated with this series and there is no indication that Smith assumed these specimens to represent *unicornis*.

The only known species of *Empusa* that occurs in China is *Empusa pennicornis* (Pallas, 1773) from the landlocked Xinjiang autonomous region in the northwest. If type locality of *unicornis* is correct, it would make *pennicornis* a junior synonym of this species. However, although the original description of *unicornis* is rather detailed for the time period, it is not specific enough to diagnose it apart from other *Empusa* without the type specimen. Thus, without a type specimen with which to compare the two species, it is impossible to draw a firm conclusion as to their synonymy, which renders *unicornis* a *nomen dubium*.

Empusa unicornis (Linné, 1763) **nomen dubium**

Gryllus (Mantis) unicornis Linné, 1763

Gryllus (Mantis) unicornis Johansson, 1763 **attributio erroris**

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-pectinicornis. *Systema Naturae*, 1767: 691. Linné introduced this name in the 12th edition of *Systema Naturae* as an objective synonym for *unicornis*, placing it within the newly upgraded genus *Mantis*. He offered no justification for the introduction of this synonym and did not expressly propose *pectinicornis* as a replacement name for *unicornis*. Rather, Linné just republished the original description summary of *unicornis* under *pectinicornis* and cited the original description of the former from *Amoenitates Academicæ* Volume 6 as the only reference. This action is unlike the maneuver that Linné made by referencing the original description of *masculus* under *oratoria*. In the former case, Linné's 1767 description of *oratoria* matches the original description of *oratoria* from 1758 and there was no remnant of the description of *masculus* included in the brief treatment. In the case of *pectinicornis*, the 1767 description matches the original description of *unicornis* nearly verbatim:

Description summary of *unicornis* from 1763: “*thorace laevi, elytris viridibus, alis apice striatis, vertice subulato, antennis pectinatis*”

Description summary of *pectinicornis* from 1767: “*thorace laevi, elytris viridibus, alis oblique striatis, vertice subulato, antennis pectinatis*”

Given this near replication of descriptions between the two names and the single conjoining reference that was cited, it is evident that Linné created an objective synonym for *unicornis* by introducing *pectinicornis*. His rationale for this action is open for interpretation.

In 2004, Roy listed *pectinicornis* as a potential synonym of *hedenborgii* Stal, 1871 and *unicornis* as a potential synonym of *pennicornis* (Pallas, 1773). As *pectinicornis* is the objective synonym for *unicornis*, they represent the same central Asian species. Thus, *pectinicornis* has no association with the northern African/western Asian species *hedenborgii*. Roy also listed both of Linné's names as *nomen dubium*. Given that the original description of *unicornis/pectinicornis* fully aligns with male *pennicornis* from central Asia, there is no reason to doubt the application of this name, despite the loss of the holotype.

Empusa unicornis (Linné, 1763)
= *Mantis pectinicornis* Linné, 1767 **n. syn.**

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